

Uie in oënskou

Die gebruik van multisaad-ueproppe, wat die eerste keer in Saailingnuus aan Suid-Afrikaanse kwekers beskryf is, word 'n gewilde en winsgewende metode om uie te kweek. Die hoofgebruik tot dusver was om bolletjies vir vroeë produksie te vervang, en waar die groeivoordele van basterkultivars verkies word.

Model 200 Speedling-laaie word gewoonlik verkies. Tot tien sade word per sel geplant, met gevolglik sowat ses saailinge per prop. Proppe word teen 'n spasiëring van omtrent 20 x 40 cm uitgeplant, met 'n gevolglike plantbevolking van 600 000 tot 800 000 plante per hektaar, of 125 000 proppe per hektaar.

'n Belangrike punt om te onthou wanneer uieproppe gebruik word, is dat groei nie deur spanning belemmer moet word nie. As dit gebeur, neem dit die saailinge 'n ruk om te herstel voordat groei hervat word, sodat die voordele van 'n vroeë opbrengs verlore gaan. Indien moontlik, moet proppe direk uit die laaie in die land uitgeplant word, omdat uiewortels die groeiemedium nie baie goed bind nie. Die proppe bly delikaat en verbrokkel maklik.

Die opbrengsvoordele van proppe teenoor bolletjies spruit hoofsaaklik uit 'n toereikende plantbevolking en lewenskragtige saailinge. 'n Vermindering in barsting, vroeë saadskiet en onbemarkbare groottes dra verder tot die voordele van die propstelsel by.

'n Kweker in die Brits-gebied het 4 000 sakkies per hektaar uit proppe geoes, vanaf middel-Julie. Die opbrengs uit bolletjies wat tegelykertyd gekweek is, was slegs 2 000 sakkies per hektaar. Hierdie vroeëheid en opbrengs is verkry ondanks die feit dat daar nie 'n vroeë kultivar, soos byvoorbeeld Sonic, gebruik is nie.

In die OVS het die oes van direk-gesaaide Sonic in Augustus vanjaar begin. By die skryf hiervan, was die verwagte oes heelwat meer as 6 000 sakkies per hektaar, en daar is R18 tot R20 per sakkie op die mark ontvang. Die boer se opmerking teenoor die Starke Ayres verteenwoordiger se waarskuwing dat hy liefies nie te veel van 'n nuwe kultivar moet plant nie, kan nie hier gedruk word nie!

Daar is duidelik 'n dubbele neiging by uieproduksie. Om die vroeë, hoëprys-markvenster te bereik, gebruik party

Multisaad-ueproppe, boere maak wins op die vroeë mark.

kwekers 'n vinnige kultivar soos Sonic, terwyl dit lyk of ander kwekers vroeg kan oes deur die multisaad-propstelsel te gebruik. 'n Mens wil dus wonder hoe 'n kombinasie sou werk. ▼

Uieproppe lyk anders, maar die opbrengs bring 'n glimlag.

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Begonias Beat the Blues!

Peter Kruger

The fibrous-rooted Begonias from Benary, Germany, have made a strong impression on the nursery trade and gardening public in South Africa.

The Olympia begonias were introduced by Kudu Seed last year. Initially only available in red, pink and white, the novelty salmon-orange has been released this year. All of these flower colours are effectively contrasted against the light green foliage of the plants. Their abundant production of large flowers and their strong, pure colours make the Olympias the leading begonia series in South Africa today.

Olympia salmon orange

Begonias are extremely versatile plants and with the introduction of the F1 Olympias, their application has been further extended. It is now possible to grow Begonias in full sun in most parts of South Africa. They are naturally fairly frost sensitive and should only be exposed to the elements in frost-free areas.

The Olympia Begonias are ideal for use in containers and as bedding plants. They make an extremely inviting display when planted in a six-pack for nursery outlets.

Olympia white

At present, the seed of Olympia Begonias is available in glass vials of an eighth of a gram (approximately 8 750 seeds). Kudu Seed has also recently introduced these Begonias in pelleted form for easier sowing, manually and mechanically. This facilitates the use of Speedling trays for propagation.

The Olympia Begonias have a germination capacity of more than 80% and should be sown about four months before intended date of sale. They germinate best with bottom heat in winter, the recommended germinating temperature being 21°C.

Germination is complete three weeks after sowing and seedlings are ready for pricking out after five weeks. Begonia seedlings prefer to be watered with room temperature water.

The plants prefer a loose, humus-enriched soil and should be fed with a

general fertilizer while in the nursery. The recommended growth retardant on Olympia Begonias is Cycocel (CCC) at 0,05% concentration.

If you have the economic blues, try the Olympia Begonias to lift your spirits. After all, can you really resist them? ▼

Olympia red

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EDITOR'S VIEW

Several issues which are important to the seedling industry are addressed in this *Seedling News*. The potential for careless growers to spread serious diseases must not be ignored. By the same token, application of chemicals to seedlings in the nursery is a potentially efficient means of treating field crops. In both cases more imaginative research is required to prevent one and to promote the other.

The differences between traditional bedding plant growers and the relatively new vegetable/forestry seedling industry are rapidly

disappearing. Not only are more seedling growers supplying traditional bedding plants, but more bedding plant growers are adopting techniques and technology developed for large scale seedling propagation. This interchange of ideas and technology is benefitting both groups.

Keeping up with developments in plant breeding is a major undertaking. No sooner do you spend time with one aspect of the seed trade, than another suddenly shows a major breakthrough. It is precisely these problems which the Starke Ayres Research and Technical departments tackle by maintaining close contact with breeders around the world, accessing this material for local trials, arranging semi-commercial trials with co-operating farmers and finally distributing this information via magazines, farmer's days and direct contact.

It may be argued that this information is valuable and should be sold. In the short term, this is a valid argument, however, after over one hundred years of serving the South African farmer, Starke Ayres has a longer term view. An open attitude towards sharing information benefits all. It is therefore disturbing that there appears to be a trend in the Seedling Growers Association to try and prevent the spread of information to potential new nurserymen. ▼

Seedling News

The cost of duplication of articles in English and Afrikaans is prohibitive. However, any readers requiring a specific article translated are welcome to request a typescript copy. Please include a self-addressed stamped envelope with your request and specify the desired article clearly.

Die kostes verbonde aan die plasing van artikels in beide Engels en Afrikaans is ontsaglik duur. Lesers wat 'n vertaling van enige artikel benodig is egter welkom om daarvoor aan te vra. Stuur 'n self-gedresseerde koevert met die nodige posseël aan ons en dui duidelik aan watter artikel u benodig. ▼

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Osoon-bewus?

Baie kwekerymense is besorg oor die al-groter-wordende hope uitskotsaailinglaaie in hul kwekerye. Dan is hulle boonop besorg dat hulle gebruik van polistireen-saailinglaaie dalk tot omgewingsaftakeling mag bydra, veral tot beskadiging van die osoonlaag.

Speedling laaie word deur 'n inspuitvormingsproses vervaardig, waardeur polistireenkorreltjies wat 'n blaasmiddel bevat, vergroot word om die vorm te vul. Die gas wat in hierdie proses gebruik word, is pentaan, 'n natuurlike gas wat geproduseer word tydens anaërobiese biochemiese degradasie by mense en diere, en wat ook 'n bestanddeel van 'moerasgas' is. Polistireen en pentaan is albei suiwer waterstofkoolstowwe (d.w.s. dit bestaan volledig uit koolstof- en waterstofmolekules).

Die gebruik van CFC-gasse vir die vervaardiging van polistireenprodukte is feitlik totaal uitgedien in prosesse wat van ekstrusie gebruik maak, en het nog nooit in inspuitvorming 'n rol gespeel nie. Die vervaardiging van polistireenprodukte, veral deur inspuitvorming, lei tot geen omgewingsaftakeling nie (afgesien van die verbruik van energie). Geen toksiese gasse word gebruik of gevorm nie. Selfs die pentaangas, wat geleidelik uit die

korreltjies uitlek, word gou deur 'n fotochemiese reaksie in die atmosfeer afgebreek.

Hoe daar van Speedling laaie ontslae geraak kan word (veral die nuwes wat net een keer gebruik word) verdien aandag. Daar is 'n paar moontlikhede. Die smelt van vergrote stireen terug na die oorspronklike kompakte polistireen vir hergebruik sal waarskynlik nie werk nie, vanweë hul wye spreiding, hul kontaminasie met grond, en die gespesialiseerde toerusting wat nodig is. Verbranding vir energieherwinning is 'n opsie in plekke waar verbranders gebruik word. Voldoende lug en geskikte temperature (omtrent 1 000 °C) is nodig vir skoon verbranding. Stireen wat buite verbrand word, brand nie skoon nie, en te veel roet ontstaan. In die geval van 'n vuur, is daar gewoonlik geen omgewingsgevaar vanweë toksiese gasse of waterbesoedeling nie. Die dampe wat ontstaan, is soortgelyk aan die wat deur brandende hout veroorsaak word.

Polistireenuitskot wat tot 'n gespesifiseerde fynheid gemaal word, word in party lande amptelik erken as 'n stof wat die grond verbeter. Dit word in verpottingsgrond gebruik, vir die verbetering van belugting en dreinerings in kleigrond, en as vuller in slootdreineringsstelsels. Tuinontwerpers

kan onvermaalde uitskotlaaie nuttig vind vir die bou van berms en lae keermuurtjies, waar die laaie met grond gevul en met dekplante beplant word. Die polistireen neig om poreus te wees, en plantwortels kan tussen die korreltjies deurdring. Polistireen is biologies onaktief en skei nie stowwe af wat die lug, grond of water mag besoedel nie.

Die hope onooglike, brandgevaarlike uitskot Speedling laaie by kwekerye kan in 'n welkome inkomstebron omskep word! ▼

Organic Growers

The use of purely organic fertilizers for seedling propagation has been rather a hit or miss business. Kompel Organic Plant Food can be used successfully to fertilize seedlings in the Speedling system.

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Grass plugs — the new option

Establishment of lawns and pastures by using grass plugs is becoming a popular choice. In fact landscapers, in particular, are making use of the technique more fully by applying it to a wider range of ground covers.

Proponents of the technique claim distinct cost advantages as well as considerable time saving compared to establishment from runners. As an example, let's look at the costs involved in establishing a domestic lawn with Bayview.

Speed of cover is determined by vigour of the plugs, season, availability of water and nutrients, and density of plugs. Density of planting varies from five to twenty five plugs per square metre. The most commonly used is 10–17 plugs (spacing on a 25 and 20 cm grid pattern). These can give full cover in as little as six weeks. At R50 per thousand plugs, a domestic lawn of 150 m² at 17 plugs per square metre would require less than three thousand (13 trays of 200 plugs). Planting material would cost between R130 and R150. Provided the surface is reasonably prepared, the expense of full seedbed preparation is avoided. Transplanting plugs is a very much quicker operation than putting in runners. Time to cover is far quicker because growing plants are transplanted rather than dormant

runners. The after care and control of watering, while necessary, is not nearly as critical as for runners or seed.

Another use for grass plugs is for instant grassing at shows and expos. The commonly used ryegrass on hessian has its place, but is obviously an artificial lawn and does not stand walking on. Also, it is not long before the rapidly growing ryegrass is too long. Trays of well established Bayview

and other groundcovers can be laid down in much the same way as carpet tiles. They are robust and provide adequate nutrient and water reserves to keep the grass healthy for a fair length of time. The appearance is that of a well established lawn and can be walked on with no more damage than an outside lawn. Stiletto heels even sink in realistically!

DIY Seedlings

A new concept in retail marketing is being launched this spring by Starke Ayres. Many hobby gardeners would like to extend their activity in their favourite hobby to include growing their own seedlings. Up till now, the necessary products have not been marketed as a package.

DIY Seedlings is marketed with the popular model 24 Speedling tray as the central product. This is attractively packaged for the retail sector in an eye-catching yellow and green wrapper. Full details for growing seedlings are printed on the side, with mention of suitable products such as growing medium, fertilizer, fungicides and pesticides.

DIY Seedlings capture the imagination!

Garden centre personnel will welcome the ease with which a gardener can be introduced to the art of DIY Seedlings. There is plenty of scope for creating an attractive and informative display using the Kompel, Kombat and Kudu ranges of products.

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FOCUS ON CLUB ROOT

Bruce Paterson

Here to stay? What is the magnitude of the problem?

Having been identified on numerous previous occasions it has again raised its head in areas of South Africa in recent months and would appear to be on the increase. We need to get to know the Do's and Don'ts of this disease and stop it now before it becomes a problem of much larger proportion.

Clubroot is a destructive disease of Cabbage, Cauliflower, Broccoli, Brussels sprouts, Kohlrabi, Chinese cabbage, Radish and Turnip. Once infested in a soil the fungus may persist for many years, by means of dormant spores which remain in the soil and only become active under optimum water and temperature regimes.

Symptoms first appear, usually in the more waterlogged areas, there being a wilting of the plants during the heat of the day. On closer investigation it will be found that the roots are extremely distorted and swollen, depending on the severity of the infection. These swollen galls are also a source of spores as they gradually decompose in the soil. Direct seeded crops, if infected very early, seldom develop into much at all.

Infection is favoured by acid soils with adequate moisture and temperature. Infections do also occur at pH > 7,0 under optimum conditions for the fungus.

The distinctive clubs caused by the club root fungus.

The fungus may easily be introduced to the field by a number of means:

- (i) movement of infected plants or transplants,
- (ii) movement of infected soil on farm machinery,
- (iii) run-off water which may carry the immobile, resistant, resting spores into irrigation water,
- (iv) manure from animals fed infected culls or plants.

At present there is no economical way of controlling it. Water, where possible, should be clean and free of contamination up stream, i.e. avoid tailwater from contaminated fields. Rotations of two or more years without crucifer crops has been found to reduce soil inoculation. Heavy liming has been used to some effect on commercial scales.

We must be aware of the problem and tackle it on its first appearance. Too many farmers are inclined to play their cards close to the chest! The entire catchment may be infected and a combined strategy should be planned. ▼

These twisted and distorted roots are the result of root spirality and binding. Plant growth is stunted, but club root infection is not evident.

AN UPDATE

Ned Kerr

The club root fungus has been one of the major pathogens on Brassicas (Cabbage family) in Europe for nearly a century, and much research has been done on methods of controlling it. All of this work has shown variable results for two major reasons. The ability of this primitive fungus to mutate readily has resulted in many races, and the intensity of the spore load in the soil affects the efficacy of chemical treatment. This conclusion was reached by Professor John Colhoun¹, at Queens University, Belfast, almost half a century ago, and appears to be as valid today as it was then.

In this context, papers published by the Bristol Journal of Plant Pathology between 1982 and 1986 by Jones-Ingram and Dixon, Phelps, Barnes and co-workers and Dixon and Robinson, are of interest. Claims have been made for the effectiveness of a number of chemicals including the systemic MBC compound, thiophanatemethyl and quitozene, best overall according to John Colhoun; none has shown any improvement on the use of mercury either as mercuric chloride as a solution at planting stations, or mercurous chloride as a paste applied to the roots of transplants. Of course, the use of mercury compounds is prohibited today in many countries, including South Africa.

Apparently, liming is mainly effective when the spore load is low; when the soil is heavily contaminated, liming may be regarded as only effective if the temperature and/or water level of the soil are not optimum, or near optimum, for infection and disease development. If Professor Colhoun's deduction from his findings is correct, then control through liming can only be regarded as erratic.

Currently many races of the fungus are known to exist and these seem to appear in mixtures in soil where one or other may prove to be dominant. This would greatly help in explaining why cultivars show variable results from one locality to another, or season by season.

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Although it might appear self-evident, it was shown some forty years ago that the spore load in the soil had a distinct bearing on the level of tolerance shown by different cultivars.

Overall, it is accepted that an integrated approach is essential in coping with the potential ravages of this pathogen. A lower spore load can be produced by adequate rotation, water cleanliness, general farm hygiene (with particular reference to implements), liming, and chemicals with some potential for destroying germinating spores, are all relevant, even where so-called resistant or tolerant cultivars are available.

Because of the ease with which spores germinate at high moisture levels and the mobile phase, known as zoospores, which can move through the soil water, ridging for better drainage should have some positive effect. Generally, it has been observed that infection is at its heaviest in depressed areas in the land where water-logging can occur.

Cultivars with tolerance or resistance to as wide a range of races as possible is the ultimate step in integrated control. All or most of the more promising open-pollinated cultivars tested in Europe gave a variable performance and none showed any reliable level of tolerance.

With the advent of hybrids in cabbage and other Brassica species, the chances of combining desirable genes giving

Kenzan cabbage.

tolerance to a range of races of the pathogen are much enhanced.

A responsibility rests on seedsmen, with adequate facilities and personnel, to screen as much material as possible which has any claim to tolerance available from plant breeders on an international level. Starke Ayres, through its research department, has been doing such screening for some time and, thus far, the cabbage cultivar,

Kenzan, has been introduced to the local market. ▼

Reference

1 Professor J. Colhoun; M.Agr. Ph.D. D.Sc. was Professor of Plant Pathology, University of Manchester from 1952-86 and Pro-Vice Chancellor for some years until his retirement in 1988.

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Protecting transplants as plugs

Warrick Nelson

Loading the seedling root plug with protective chemicals is not a new concept. English researchers have tested it for some time with their module seedlings to protect cabbage-family seedlings from various pests normally only a problem after transplanting.

What are the possibilities for this concept in South African nursery practice? Firstly, it must be remembered that none of the suggestions considered in this article is registered for use or has even been tested in practice. The intention is to stimulate ideas and possibly arrive at practical measures after the relevant research work has been done.

Two basic protection requirements will be considered. Firstly, the problem of fungal root diseases in vegetable seedlings. The fungicide quinterozone is registered in South Africa for a number of crops against a range of root diseases. An obvious extension of usage of the product could be to treat cabbage seedlings against clubroot. The broad spectrum of activity of this chemical may prove worthwhile using on onion seedlings to protect against white rot, or on pepper and tomato seedlings to control and protect against Southern blight.

Termite damage to forestry seedlings after transplanting can be devastating. Carbosulfan may prove a suitable chemical to apply to seedlings before they leave the nursery. Applied as a foliar spray/root plug drench or mixed into the growing medium as controlled release granules, this chemical shows potential to alleviate termite problems. Carbosulfan is not restricted to controlling termite damage to forest seedlings. It could be used on a wide range of crop seedlings, including some vegetables, to control the spread of a number of insect pests.

This article may appear to be promoting the use of more chemical products in horticulture to the detriment

of the environment. Application of necessary chemicals under the more closely managed conditions normally found in nurseries will reduce the risks of chemical usage. The greater concentration of plants in the seedling stage could result in a marked reduction in the quantity of chemical required to have the same field effectiveness. This technology would not only have an economic impact on pest and disease control, but also a beneficial environmental impact.

Bright lights may be glowing on the horizon, but until registration for use of chemicals in this manner is passed, they are illegal. Please be responsible in the use of farm chemicals. ▼

Foresters!

Styrodip, the well known root-pruning agent used on Speedling trays, now has a partner in the form of Plazdip. Where hard plastic seedling containers are preferred, Plazdip should be applied to prevent the formation of a root cage.

Many foresters have experienced problems with root growth in hard plastic containers. Even with a square profile, roots have been found to spiral. Root cages allow for quick and easy

extraction of seedlings, but the lack of roots in the centre of the plug results in the growing medium falling out. Where this occurs, seedlings are transported and transplanted with naked, unprotected roots which are subject to root distortion.

Plazdip is available in the same pack sizes as Styrodip. These are as five and twenty five litre drums of Ready-to-use or as a Concentrate in a fifty litre barrel. ▼

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Disposable trays offer both nurseryman and customer many advantages. Carry-over of diseases and the hassles of sterilising porous trays are eliminated. Users of seedlings prefer to receive seedlings in trays, thus taking advantage of the natural protective and insulating properties of polystyrene. Gone is the bother of returning trays to the nursery (very few operate on this basis anyway) and the arguments over who is responsible for damaged trays.

Two sectors of the seedling industry have shown particular interest in disposable trays. Foresters have always tended to prefer purchasing seedlings in trays. With their justified concern over root protection, they will be pleased to have this avenue reopened. Model 98 trays for pines and other forest species transplanted under less-than-ideal conditions, are proving economical.

Lawn grass plug growers and users will be particularly interested in the special disposable model 200 tray. The modern design offers a greater plug volume **without increasing cell depth**. The special characteristics of grass plugs allows an even lower density to be used, thus reducing prices to an absolute minimum.

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Changing gear with Ned Kerr

Ned Kerr has been a familiar character in the seed industry for many years. His stamina, wealth of technical information and stock of amusing anecdotes were his trade mark around the world.

Ned was born and schooled in Ireland. He saw active service in WW2 as well as spending some time delving into the finer points of whiskey manufacture while a POW. After attaining his BSc (Hons) in plant pathology, he decided that Africa held more opportunities for him. He held a post in the government services in Southern Rhodesia, during which time he represented the Federation at the UN FAO in Rome.

Ned joined Starke Ayres after the break up of the Federation and took over from Alan Starke as Technical Director. Ned is responsible for many of

the new cultivars released on the South African market. Amongst these are Floradade tomato, hybrid cabbages such as Green Star and Green Coronet, Long Canner beetroot and Bayview lawn grass.

After 25 years with Starke Ayres, Ned has decided to retire from the more active aspects of the seed industry. Although he will retain his links with Starke Ayres on a consultancy basis, Ned feels that he will now have the time to get down to writing a text book on vegetable production.

Ned, it is our privilege to have worked with you and to have had the benefit of your expertise. On behalf of all your colleagues and those who know you, we wish you and Rita a rewarding retirement and many happy hours next to the babbling brook at Rhein Cottage. ▼

Forestry seedlings

Warrick Nelson

The problems experienced on some sites by forestry companies are not yet fully explained. However, a number of possible reasons have been put forward to account for the lodging and even complete toppling of trees.

The problem can be divided into three basic categories. Firstly that of poor soils or site preparation. This is relatively easily established and explained. Secondly that of unstable trees and poor root systems. This report gives some insight into this. Thirdly there is the "ball and socket" problem where trees snap off at soil level, even though they may have an apparently good root system.

From field investigations, it would appear that the second and third symptoms are not related. Some trees exhibiting "ball and socket" deformities have good root systems, while some have obviously deformed roots. There is some speculation that this symptom is related to genetics, to management in the nursery or care of the seedling between the nursery and transplanting. It is clear that no simple solution is yet available.

A trial conducted at Starke Ayres has demonstrated the importance of correct transplanting technique. In this trial, two treatments included deliberate poor transplanting technique which bent the root plug. The expected root deformities are obvious. However, in addition to the transplanting treatment there was a pruning treatment in which the lower third of the root plug was removed.

From left to right, good transplanting and not pruned, poor transplanting unpruned and poor transplanting with a pruned root plug.

A number of thickened root tips typically occur at the base of root plugs of older seedlings. This has been suggested as a cause of root deformities after transplanting and was dubbed the "air-pruned club-root syndrome". In this trial, it was found that with correct transplanting, no obvious difference in subsequent root growth (after six months growth) could be detected. Saplings, both pruned and unpruned, displayed mainly single tap roots, but up to three were evident. These tap roots did not appear to have any spirality.

Possibly of greater interest is the evidence that pruned root plugs tended to show far less root deformities with poor transplanting technique. This confirms the intuitive observation that a longer root plug is more prone to bending during transplanting. Growers using deep plugs should pay even more attention to the transplanting operation.

The old technique of standing the seedling on the bottom of the planting

hole followed by heavy firming in is totally inappropriate to Speedling seedlings. Rather, the seedling should be held against the edge of the planting hole and the soil firmed against it with a sideways action. No firming from above is necessary. ▼

Brinjals are very popular for eastern European and Asian cuisine. Their popularity in the average Western diet will only improve with the introduction of modern cultivars bred for improved flavour. Two outstanding new hybrids have recently become available. **Black King** is the traditional egg-shape with a very dark, almost black skin colour. It is very tolerant to high temperatures, with none of the bitter flavour associated with more traditional cultivars. **Farmers Long** is still something of a novelty. It is not a traditional shape and has a pleasant purple colour. **Farmers Long** has already gained acceptance for many Indian dishes and is rapidly gaining popularity for stir-frying.

Romanesco is a traditional form of cauliflower/broccoli from Italy. It is proving extremely popular as a novelty line and has taken the world by storm. Although still somewhat variable in quality, modern breeding techniques are being used to bring about improvements. It is likely that the introduction of improved strains, possibly even hybrids, will result in the name Romanesco being used to describe the type of vegetable. Until then, we are left wondering whether it tastes more like broccoli or cauliflower.

If you are somewhat impatient and feel that Green Star is too slow to mature, try **Bravo**. Heads begin to firm and grow bigger daily, so prevent uneven growth to reduce the risk of splitting. Under correct conditions, **Bravo** has demonstrated good standability after optimal harvest time. Limited seed stocks are available this season.

Revito blomkool is 'n vroeë kultivar met 'n opbrengspotensiaal wat met laat kultivars vereenselwig word. Goeie beskerming help om sonbrand op die puikgehalte koppe te verhoed, selfs wanneer daar vir die Kersmark gekweek word. Kopvorming in die middel van die somer is natuurlik buiteseisoenproduksie vir blomkool. Die beste saaiyd vir **Revito** is ietwat later, vir herfs-oes.

Die mark vir voorafverpakte **wortels** groei vinnig. **Douceur** het 'n groot indruk gemaak op kwekers wat 'n tydjie gelede aan die Fase 2 semi-kommersiële proewe meegewerk het. Vir 'n feitlik ononderbroke voorraad die hele jaar deur, vir voorafverpakking of as babawortels, is **Douceur** omtrent onvergelykbaar!

Dubbeldoeltamatiekultivars bied kwekers baie voordele. Vir die varsmark bied hulle 'n ferm vrug met goeie raklewe aan ranke wat geen stelliasies benodig nie. Verwerkers stel meer in opbrengs en verwerkingseienskappe belang. **FMX 785** is die eerste kultivar in hierdie klas wat albei markte bevredig.

LETTUCE

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New **WINTER** heading lettuce capable of producing uniform, heavy heads of exceptional quality even under severe winter temperatures. Coarsely frilled wrapper leaves provide good head cover in the field and protection during transportation. Excellent performer from late autumn to early spring.

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